

Experimental Investigation on Mechanical Properties of SiC and Rice Husk Ash Reinforced Aluminium Hybrid Metal Matrix Composite

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ABSTRACT

The intention of the current research work is to investigate the mechanical properties of the hybrid composite. A356.2 alloy has been chosen as the matrix material. Silicon carbide was used as reinforcement at weight percentages of 0%, 1.5%, 3%, and 4.5%, and rice husk ash was used as an additional reinforcement at weight percentages of 0%, 1.5%, 3%, and 4.5%. The stir-casting method is used to prepare the hybrid aluminium composite material. The mechanical properties of the prepared composites were investigated. The experimental results indicate that ultimate tensile strength and hardness increase with the increment in reinforcement quantity, but percentage elongation decreases.

Keywords: hybrid composites, A356.2 alloy, silicon carbide, rice husk ash, mechanical properties

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1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys are the second most widely used metallic engineering material after steel. Aluminium alloys are widely used in transportation sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and marine industries, as well as in construction, electrical and electronics, and consumer goods. This widespread use is mainly due to their excellent properties, including low weight, good formability, and high corrosion resistance. The primary challenge in high-temperature lightweight engineering is microstructural degradation, which leads to a significant reduction in stiffness and strength. The use of metal matrix composites with suitably designed reinforcement architectures is expected to

mitigate this effect. A composite material is a combination of two materials with different physical and chemical properties. A composite material is made up of a matrix and a reinforcement phase. Aluminium, copper, iron, manganese, nickel, titanium, and related alloys are commonly used as metal matrices. Among these, aluminium is the most widely preferred for metal matrix composites due to its low density, high electrical and thermal conductivity, and excellent corrosion resistance. Silicon, nickel, zinc, copper, magnesium, and manganese are commonly used alloying elements to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of monolithic aluminium. Reinforcements improve the strength, stiffness, and temperature resistance of aluminium matrix composites. Ceramic particulates are widely used as reinforcements in AMMCs to enhance strength, hardness, corrosion resistance, and wear resistance. Figure 1 shows different reinforcements used for the development of MMCs. Aluminium metal-matrix composites (AMMCs) exhibit significantly superior mechanical and physical properties compared to unreinforced aluminium alloys. Figure 2 presents a wide range of applications of aluminium metal-matrix composites in engineering, transportation, and recreation. The primary requirements of materials for modern engineering applications include low weight, high strength, high stiffness, and good wear resistance. These requirements cannot be fully satisfied by single-reinforced metal matrix composites alone. Hybrid metal-matrix composites can be prepared by reinforcing two or more reinforcing materials into a metal matrix. In recent years, hybrid metal-matrix composites (HMMCs) have attracted significant attention from researchers due to their superior mechanical performance compared with single-reinforced metal-matrix composites and monolithic alloys.

Figure 1: Different reinforcements used for the development of MMCs

Figure 2: Applications of aluminium metal-matrix composites

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

D. Siva Prasad et al. [1] fabricated the aluminium – rice hush ash composite by stir casting to investigate the mechanical properties. Percentage of rice hush ash was varied from 0 to 8wt% in steps of 2wt%. Results indicated that the ultimate tensile strength and hardness of the composite is higher than the base matrix. Also, the ultimate tensile strength and hardness of the composite increased with increase in weight percent of rice hush ash in the matrix.

A.P.S.V.R.Subrahmanyam et al. [2] investigated the mechanical properties of rice husk ash (RHA) reinforced aluminium metal matrix composites. The aluminum alloy (A356.2) is used as the matrix metal for the fabrication of the composites that has been reinforced with 0 wt. %, 2 wt. %, 4 wt. % and 8 wt. % of RHA. The result of this investigation showed that the tensile strength, percentage elongation, hardness and impact strength of the composite increased with increase in weight percent of rice husk ash in the matrix.

Gaurav Arora et al. [3] prepared a hybrid metal matrix composite using an aluminium 6351 alloy as a matrix and silicon carbide and rice husk ash as reinforcement materials. Silicon carbide and rice husk ash were mixed using the ball-milling process in various wt.% proportions of 2:6, 4:4 and 6:2 to produce AA6351 green hybrid composites using the stir casting technique. The samples are prepared according to ASTM standards and tested to find the various mechanical properties. The result shows that the hybrid composites with the reinforcement wt.% proportion of 6:2 silicon carbide to rice husk ash showed the best results of hardness, tensile strength and wear testing compared with the other wt.% proportions of the reinforcements.

Uppada Rama Kanth et al. [4] investigated mechanical behavior of Al–Zn alloy based composite filled with SiC/fly ash (ratio 1:1 weight of mixture) at 5 and 10 wt% filler loading and fabricated by stir casting. The researchers observed that the ultimate tensile strength, yield strength and hardness increased with the increase in percentage of reinforcement in the matrix alloy.

Satheesh M et al. [5] have manufactured Al 6061 matrix reinforced with 10% SiC constant and varying coconut shell ash weight fractions of 2%, 4%, 6% 8% and 10%. Mechanical properties of the fabricated hybrid composites are investigated. The hardness and tensile strength of Al6061-SiC-8% CSA hybrid composite increased by 46% and 47.31% respectively. However, the addition of 10% CSA decreases the hardness by 5% and tensile strength by 14.80% when compared to hybrid composite containing 8%CSA.

In this work, an attempt has been made to prepare A356.2 alloy composites by adding silicon carbide and rice husk ash reinforcement particles into the matrix by using a stir casting methodology. The silicon carbide and rice husk ash were added in 0%, 3%, 6%, and 9% by weight to the molten metal. The objective of the present investigation is to determine the mechanical properties of the aluminum hybrid matrix composites by adding reinforcement particles into the aluminum alloy.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the current investigation, Aluminium (A356.2) has been used as the matrix phase and silicon carbide and rice husk ash as the reinforcement phase.

3.1 A356.2 alloy

A356.2 is a cast aluminum–silicon–magnesium alloy widely used in automotive and aerospace industries due to its excellent combination of strength, castability, and corrosion resistance. Table -1 represents the chemical composition of the A356.2 alloy.

3.2 Silicon carbide

Silicon carbide is a compound of silicon and carbon with the chemical formula SiC. It is originally produced by a high temperature electro-chemical reaction of sand and carbon. It is the most widely used non-oxide ceramic. Silicon carbide is a promising ceramic material with excellent thermomechanical characteristics, including high thermal conductivity, excellent mechanical properties, and excellent resistance to wear and oxidation.

3.3 Rice husk ash

Rice husk ash is a ceramic oxide, primarily composed of silica (SiO₂), which exhibits high hardness and brittle behavior. Rice husk is the outermost layer of protection encasing a rice grain. It has a convex shape and yellowish colour. The rice husk was collected from a rice mill. The rice husk then were washed with water and dried at room temperature for 1 day. Dried rice husk was heated to 200 °C for 1 hour in order to remove the moisture and organic matter. The yellow colour of the rice husk changed into black colour and then heated to 600°C for 12 hours to remove the carbonaceous material. After completion of this process, the colour again changed from black to grayish white. Table -2 represents the chemical composition of rice husk ash. A composition of composite specimens is shown in table-3.

Table 1: Chemical composition of A356.2 alloy

Elements	Composition (%)
Silicon (Si)	6.5 – 7.5
Magnesium (Mg)	0.25 – 0.45
Iron (Fe)	≤ 0.15
Copper (Cu)	≤ 0.20
Manganese (Mn)	≤ 0.10
Zinc (Zn)	≤ 0.10
Titanium (Ti)	≤ 0.20
Nickel (Ni)	≤ 0.05
Aluminum (Al)	Balance

Table 2: Chemical composition of rice husk ash.

Compound	Wt%
SiO ₂	94.8
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.61
CaO	1.41
K ₂ O	1.33
MnO	0.28
TiO ₂	0.17
CuO	0.04

Table 3: Compositions of composite specimens

Weight % of A356.2 alloy	Weight % of SiC	Weight % of RHA	Weight % of reinforcement
100	0	0	0
97	1.5	1.5	3
94	3.0	3.0	6
91	4.5	4.5	9

3.4 Preparation of composites

The stir casting method is used for the manufacturing of metal matrix composites. This method helps to achieve a uniform distribution of reinforcement in the matrix material. The A356.2 alloy is the base material, and SiC and rice husk ash are used as the reinforcement particles. Initially, pure aluminium alloy was cut into small pieces to minimize the melting time and maximize the effective melting. The silicon carbide and rice husk ash particles were initially preheated separately at a temperature of 450-500°C for 1 hour to remove moisture and to help even distribution within the A356.2 alloy. The aluminum alloy was charged into the graphite crucible and heated to 750°C till the entire metal in the crucible was melted. After the metal alloy is completely melted,

degassing tablets are added to reduce porosity. Simultaneously, 1% by weight magnesium was added to the melt to enhance the wettability between the matrix and the reinforcements. The preheated SiC particles were added to the molten metal at a constant rate during the stirring. Stirring was continued for an additional 10 minutes after the completion of particle feeding. Then preheated rice husk ash particulates were added at a constant rate, and the stirring continued for 20 min. After 20 minutes of stirring, the complete mixture of reinforcement materials with aluminium alloy metal matrix was made. The mixture was poured into the mold, which was also preheated to 500°C for 20 minutes to obtain uniform solidification. After solidification, the composite can be cut into different shapes and sizes as per requirements.

3.5 Mechanical test

The aluminum alloy and composites specimens are further subjected to mechanical tests like tensile and hardness.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the composite specimens are presented in table-4.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of matrix and hybrid composites.

Weight % of reinforcement	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Percentage Elongation	Hardness (BHN)
0	257	7.4	65
3	301	5.9	78
6	327	5.3	95
9	364	4.8	106

4.1 Ultimate Tensile Strength

Figure 3: Ultimate tensile strength of composites

The ultimate tensile strength of the hybrid composites against wt% of silicon carbide - rice husk ash are plotted and shown in figure 3. In this research, the test results show the improvement in the ultimate tensile strength with increasing the weight percentage of SiC-RHA. This is due to the interfacial bonding between the matrix and reinforcement. Also, the addition of silicon carbide particles enhanced the strength of the base alloy. The maximum ultimate tensile strength is obtained at 4.5 wt% of silicon carbide and 4.5 wt% of rice husk ash reinforcements. It shows an improvement of up to 41.6% when compared to the A356.2 alloy. N.E. Udoe et al. [6] have used aluminium 6061 as the matrix material and rice husk ash with weight percentage (0, 2, 4, 6 & 8%) as the reinforcement to produce the composite by stir casting. The effect of reinforcement on the mechanical properties of composites was investigated. The researchers observed that the ultimate tensile strength increased with the increase in percentage of reinforcement in the matrix alloy. Palanisamy Pugalenthi et al. [7] investigated the mechanical properties of Al7075 alloy reinforced SiC and Al₂O₃ ceramic particulates fabricated through stir casting technique. Four specimens were produced with different compositions comprising SiC (3, 5, 7 and 9 wt %) and Al₂O₃ 2 wt% in all the combinations. Mechanical properties of the fabricated aluminium matrix composites are investigated. Results revealed that the tensile strength of the composite increased with increase in weight percent of reinforcements in the matrix. Anand Babu K et al. [8] investigated the influence of silicon carbide and flyash on the mechanical characterisation of aluminium hybrid metal matrix composites. The aluminium hybrid metal matrix composites are synthesized by reinforcing with an equal proportion of silicon carbide along with flyash and alumina along with flyash particulates in 3 wt%, 6 wt% and 9 wt% into the matrix alloy using a stir casting process. The results showed that the increase in weight percentage of reinforcement particles has increased the tensile strength of the aluminum hybrid composites.

4.2 Percentage elongation

Figure 4: Percentage elongation of composites

The percentage elongation of the pure and hybrid aluminium composite specimens was shown in figure-4. It can be observed from the table that the percentage elongation has decreased significantly from 7.4 % to 4.8 %. The percentage elongation of the composite decreases with increasing silicon carbide and rice husk ash content due to their hard and brittle nature, which

restricts the plastic deformation capability of the matrix. Prasanna P Kulkarni et al. [9] developed the rice husk ash reinforced composites and studied the effect of reinforcements on the mechanical properties. The aluminum (AA6063) - rice husk ash composites were fabricated by the stir casting method with different particulate weight percentages (0%, 2%, 4%, 6% and 8%). Results revealed that the elongation of composites decreased with an increase in weight percentage of rice husk ash in the matrix material. Smruti Rekha Swain et al. [10] have prepared a hybrid metal matrix composites by using aluminium alloy 1050 as the matrix material and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (0.3 wt %), silicon carbide (SiC) (0.3 wt %), and coconut shell ash (1-8 wt%) as the reinforcing material. The test samples were prepared as per ASTM standards to investigate mechanical properties. Results indicated that the elongation decreases with an increase in the weight fraction of ash in the composites. Mastan Rao Papabathina et al. [11] carried out an investigation on a stir cast aluminum hybrid composite containing equal amounts of silicon carbide and graphite from 2 to 8% in step of 2. Mechanical properties of the fabricated aluminium matrix composites are investigated. The results showed that the percentage elongation of the composite decreases with the increase in silicon carbide and graphite content.

4.3 Hardness

Figure 5: Hardness of composites

The hardness of aluminum hybrid matrix composites is shown in figure 5. The hardness of the composites increases with increasing weight percentage of silicon carbide and rice husk ash due to the presence of hard ceramic reinforcements. A maximum hardness of 106 BHN was noticed for the matrix that had 4.5 wt% of silicon carbide particles with 4.5 wt% of rice husk ash reinforcements. It is about a 63.0% enhancement in hardness when compared to the A356.2 alloy. The mechanical properties of aluminum-based composites reinforced with rice husk ash were investigated by Adnan Adib Ahamed et al [12]. Stir casting was used to develop the aluminum - rice husk ash composites samples with various rice husk ash weight percentages were produced (0, 3, 6, and 9wt. percent). The result shows that the hardness of the composites is higher than the unreinforced matrix metal and the hardness of the composites increases with increasing the weight percentage of rice husk ash. A. Anandha Moorthy et al. [13] developed hybrid aluminium Al 6061 alloy MMC reinforced with 3% graphite and varying wt% (3, 6 and 9%) fly ash. The hardness of the hybrid composite was tested. The test results revealed that the hardness of the composite is

higher than the base matrix. Also, the hardness of the composite increased with increase in the weight percent of fly ash in the matrix. Balasubramani Subramaniam et al. [14] developed hybrid aluminium matrix composites using boron carbide (B_4C) and coconut shell fly ash (CSFA) in Al 7075 matrix. The samples of Al7075 hybrid aluminium matrix composites were fabricated with different weight percentages of (0, 3, 6, 9 and 12wt%) B_4C and 3wt% of CSFA. Mechanical properties of the fabricated aluminium matrix composites are investigated. The results showed that the expansion of a weight level of B_4C reinforcement increases the hardness in the composites. Hardness of the composites increased 33% by reinforcements of 12wt% B_4C and 3wt% CSFA in aluminium 7075 alloy.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this experimental investigation, an aluminium metal matrix composite reinforced with equal weight percentages of silicon carbide and rice husk ash was fabricated using the stir casting process. Based on the experimental observations, the following conclusions have been drawn.

- The ultimate tensile strength of composite increases with the increasing amount of reinforcement. The addition of silicon carbide and rice husk ash reinforcement 3-9% to aluminium matrix increased the tensile strength by 17% to 41%.
- The hardness of the silicon carbide and rice husk ash -filled A356.2 alloy composites was found to increase with an increase in the reinforcements.
- The percentage elongation of the hybrid composites decreases with the increase in the percentage of reinforcement.

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